

Euphresco

Final Report

Project title CBS-DETECT

Euphresco Project 2019-A-318: Sampling and analysis of asymptomatic Citrus fruits and leaf litter to detect the infection of <i>Phyllosticta citricarpa</i>

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2. Short project report

2.1. Short executive summary

Inspection of *Citrus* fruits at the border for the detection of citrus black spot (CBS) is mostly based on visual examination followed by laboratory testing of fruits exhibiting suspicious symptoms. However, due to the long incubation period of *Phyllosticta citricarpa*, CBS symptoms on fruits are visible only at maturity, several months after infection. Furthermore, symptoms are usually non-specific and could be confused with other diseases such as (anthracnosis and alternariosis). *Phyllosticta citricarpa* has been reported in leaf litter in some EU citrus-growing countries although CBS symptoms were not observed on tree canopy. Recently, the pathogen has been reported for the first time in Tunisia. As a result, an EFSA project entitled “Reduce risk assessment uncertainty: suitability of Mediterranean citrus production areas for *P. citricarpa*” (GP/EFSA/ALPHA/2019/04) was established, aiming at reducing the uncertainties related to the risk of introduction of *P. citricarpa* in the Mediterranean citrus-growing areas, by improving the knowledge on CBS epidemiology and climate suitability in the Mediterranean Basin.

Although surveys have been conducted in the EU Member States, more intensive surveys must be conducted by NPPOs in EPPO citrus-producing countries to evaluate the pest status in their territory. EFSA has developed a survey card to provide guidance on how to conduct the surveys to determine the pest status in EU citrus-producing Member States and raised the need to include asymptomatic fruits in the survey. Moreover, a new cryptic *Phyllosticta* species, namely *P. paracitricarpa*, detected in lemon leaf litter in Greece, has been reported to cause “atypical” CBS symptoms on citrus fruits following artificial inoculation. So far, this species has not been included in the EU quarantine list of harmful organisms.

In Argentina and Brazil (countries where CBS is present) exporters are performing an ethephon treatment to enhance symptom expression on fruits in order to avoid that asymptomatic CBS-infected fruits will be rejected upon arrival in Europe. Such treatment could be envisaged to be included as methodology in the CBS survey plan for fruits harvested in European citrus orchards. However, concerns have been raised on the efficacy of the proposed treatment and if it could be practically feasible to be extended to imported fruits.

In the framework of this Euphresco project, an evaluation of the efficacy of the ethephon treatment has been performed before considering including this methodology as an obligatory step in survey plans.

Molecular tests, in particular real-time PCR, are already available to detect and identify *P. citricarpa* (Bonants et al., Eur. J. Plant Pathol. 109, 503–513, 2003; Meyer et al., Plant Dis. 90, 97–101, 2006; Peres et al., Plant Dis. 91, 525–531, 2007; van Gent-Pelzer et al., J. Phytopathol. 155, 357–363, 2007) and some others have recently been published (Zajc et al., Plant Pathol. 72, 548–563, 2023). However, those tests have not been validated to detect the fungus on asymptomatic citrus tissues. In addition, a critical point is that, so far, these tests do not allow the distinction between *P. citricarpa* and *P. paracitricarpa*, thus, more specific detection assays need to be developed and validated.

The project included three main activities:

- Evaluation of methods, such as the ethephon treatment or other methods, that stimulate the early development of CBS symptoms and the production of *P. citricarpa* (and *P. paracitricarpa*) pycnidia on infected citrus fruit and/or leaves; the methods have been tested and validated on citrus matter in CBS-positive countries and imported fruit;
- Evaluation of the currently available DNA extraction methods from citrus matter and of the newly developed test to detect and identify *P. citricarpa* on asymptomatic infected citrus tissues and to discriminate it from the close-related *P. paracitricarpa*; the project included also the validation of the above-mentioned tests through a test performance study (TPS);

- Development of a sampling strategy to be used for the detection of *P. citricarpa* on asymptomatic infected citrus tissues both in the field and at the entry points.

2.2. Project aims

The project includes three main Work-Packages (WPs), excluding the Coordination and the Dissemination WPs.

Work-package 2 – Methods stimulating early development of CBS symptoms and production of pycnidia on fruits and leaves.

Work-package objectives:

1. Evaluate the effectiveness and feasibility of methods to stimulate the early appearance of CBS symptoms on asymptomatic infected citrus fruits and leaves to be used in surveys and entry points (only fruits).
2. Evaluate methods to produce *P. citricarpa* fruiting bodies on citrus tissues.
3. Implement the EPPO Standard PM7/17 with methods for the detection of *P. citricarpa* on asymptomatic infected citrus plant material.

Work-package 3 – Validation of molecular detection of *P. citricarpa* in asymptomatic fruits and leaves.

The main work-package objective was to validate a molecular test for the detection of *P. citricarpa* on asymptomatic tissue.

Work-package 4 – Set up the sampling strategy.

The main work-package objective was to set up a methodology to quantify the asymptomatic samples in both WP2 and WP3

2.3. Description of the main activities

Work-package 2: Methods stimulating early development of CBS symptoms and production of pycnidia on fruits and leaves.

Task 2.1 – Development and validation of a protocol for the induction of early CBS symptoms on fruits

Sub-Task 2.1.1. Experiments in CBS-infested countries: Brazil and Tunisia

The Ethephon-based method was tested to stimulate the appearance of CBS symptoms on citrus asymptomatic fruits from positive CBS orchards.

The experimental assay was conducted according to the protocol of Baldassari et al. (*Revista Brasileira de Fruticultura* 29, 269-275, 2007).

Two Ethephon doses were used:

- 1.57 g/l of Ethephon (3.27 ml/L of commercial product)
- 2.10 g/l of Ethephon (4.37 ml/L of commercial product)

Twenty samples of *C. limon* fruits developing hard spots were analyzed by RT-PCR.

Sub-Task 2.1.2. Experiments in countries where the pathogen is NOT known to be present: Italy (CREA) and Greece (BPI).

The plant materials included *Citrus limon* imported from CBS-infested third countries (i.e., Argentina, South Africa) and *C. sinensis* and *C. limon* produced in Greece. Citrus fruits were first treated with sodium hypochlorite and/or other fungicides, as Thiabendazole, Imazalil and Pyrimethanil, in the country of origin (imported fruits). Prior to ethephon treatment all citrus

fruits were inspected visually for CBS suspect symptoms. Fruits were submerged for 1 min in tap water with Ethrel 1,57/2,10 g/L (3,27/4,37 ml/L of commercial product, respectively). Fruits were incubated at 25 °C ± 1 °C with photoperiod 12/12 h for 1 month. During the incubation period fruits were observed after the first 2 weeks and then every 7 days for the identification of suspect spots or other lesions.

If suspect symptoms were detected, isolation and culturing on appropriate media, followed by Real-time PCR (van Gent-Pelzer et al., *J. Phytopathol.* 155, 357– 363, 2007) were performed.

Task 2.2- Development and validation of a protocol for the stimulation of fungal growth for detection of *P. citricarpa* (and *P. paracitricarpa*) on green citrus leaves (Meyer et al. *South African Journal of Science* 108 (3/4), 2012. <http://dx.doi.org/10.4102/sajs.v108i3/4.602>)

The “wet-dry” method (Meyer et al., 2012) included in the new EPPO Protocol 7/17 was evaluated in terms of its effectiveness and feasibility in enrichment fungal biomass and inducing the formation of pycnidia with pycnidiospores in green citrus leaves.

Leaves were first rinsed in tap water, then surfaces were disinfected with sodium hypochlorite (1.5% NaOCl) for 2 min, followed by thorough rinsing with sterile water. Then, the following four steps were repeated for 4–10 consecutive days: (1) leaves were submerged in sterile tap water at 35 °C for 30 min, (2) excess water was removed by draining the leaves on paper towels for 5 min, (3) leaves were placed in plastic bags (250 mm x 380 mm x 20 µm) and incubated at 42 °C for 6 h, (4) leaves were air dried at room temperature (22°C – 26°C) for 17.5 h under fluorescent light in open bags. After 4-10 days, leaf material with noticeable mycelium colonization underwent PCR.

WP 3. Validation of molecular detection of *P. citricarpa* in asymptomatic fruits and leaves

Task 3.1 – Development of a molecular test. Efficacy Evaluation by Real time PCR (CREA, Italy)

DNA was extracted from Citrus leaf litter, “wet and dry” leaves and fruits (peel).

After testing different extraction methods, two protocols were developed starting from about 5 gr of leaf litter or “wet and dry” leaves and 13 gr of fruit peel (one fruit), respectively. 1-Leaf litter or fruit peels were homogenized with liquid nitrogen and a home-made CTAB extraction buffer was used for the lysis. 2-The lysate was again homogenized by “Homogenizer Fast Prep 24” and the lysis was improved by SDS adding. 3-Total DNA was precipitated by isopropanol and subsequently resuspended. 4-A subsequent purification was carried out using two different commercial kits depending on the matrix (leaf litter or fruit peel).

Efficacy Evaluation by Real time PCR

The Real-time PCR protocol was based on that developed by van Gent- Pelzer et al. (2007) and included in the EPPO diagnostic protocol PM 7/17, modified to increase the specificity of the method (accredited method at CREA-DC): the annealing/extension temperature was incremented from 60°C to 65°C; the annealing/extension time was reduced from 1 min to 30 sec; the final reaction volume was reduced to 15 microliters to decrease the cost.

The analytical sensitivity and specificity of this test were validated.

The method was tested on asymptomatic orange and lemon fruits artificially inoculated with *P. citricarpa*. Inoculation was carried out with 25 µl of 10⁵ conidia/ml on wounded peel. Molecular analysis was performed after 15 days, without the presence of symptoms.

The method was also tested on naturally infected samples: asymptomatic lemon fruit provided by ISA-CM (Tunisia). 1- upon arrival, the asymptomatic fruits were separated from those with visible symptoms; 2- the presence of *P. citricarpa* was confirmed by molecular analysis of the

CBS lesions; 3- Five pools, consisting of three symptomless fruits each, were analysed with the developed method.

Sensitivity evaluation (limit of detection):

-leaf litter and “wet and dry” leaves: 0,1 mg dry mycelium per 5 gr of matter: sensitivity was confirmed up to 15 g of matter

-peel fruit: 13 gr of peel orange spiked with 10^3 conidia; 13 gr of peel orange spiked with 1 mg of *P. citricarpa* dried mycelium: sensitivity was confirmed up to 39 g of matter

Task 3.2. Test Performance Study (TPS) of molecular test on asymptomatic tissues

Performance of two qPCR tests for detection of *P. citricarpa* was evaluated in the frame of a TPS organized by NIB, Slovenia. Participants: 13 laboratories, 11 countries: Agricultural Institute of Slovenia, Slovenia; ANSES Plant Health Laboratory, France; Benaki Phytopathological Institute/Laboratory of Mycology, Greece; Centro Attività Vivaistiche, Italy; Centro de Citricultura Sylvio Moreira, Instituto Agronômico, Brasil; CREA-DC, Council for Agricultural Research and Economics, Plant Protection and Certification, Rome, Italy; Directorate of plant protection central research institute, Mycology laboratory, Turkey; Fera Science Ltd., United Kingdom; G/D plant health and control of agricultural products DGSVCIA, Quarantine Laboratory, Tunisia; Laboratory of Plant Protection Service Lombardy Region, Italy; Main Inspectorate of Plant Health and Seed Inspection, Central Laboratory, Phytosanitary Reference Laboratory, Poland; Plant Health Laboratory, DAFM, Ireland; State Plant Protection Service of the Republic of Latvia/The National phytosanitary laboratory, Latvia.

2.4. Main results

Task 2.1 – Development and validation of a protocol for the induction of early CBS symptoms on fruits

Sub-Task 2.1.1. Experiments in CBS-infested countries: Brazil and Tunisia

- The Ethephon-based method accelerates ripening of asymptomatic *C. limon* fruits (yellowing) and is effective to develop early CBS symptoms (typical hard spots symptoms) (Fig. 1).
- The Ethephon-based method seems to be not effective to stimulate CBS symptoms on asymptomatic *C. sinensis* fruits (*Cv Valentia Late*) but enhance fruits yellowing (Fig. 1).
- The time of fruit immersion in Ethephon solution is cultivar dependent. The best results (severity index, number and diameter of CBS spots) were obtained with 1 - 5 min of immersion, depending on the cultivar.
- The most effective dose of Ethephon solution is cultivar dependent too: 1,57 - 2,1 g/l
- The minimum time of incubation for ethephon-treated fruits to develop CBS symptoms was 2 weeks.
- Number of spots: The highest values were observed for *C. limon* cv. Lunari (a mean 12 spots/fruit)
- Diameter of spots: the best values recorded were between 0.6 and 0.8 cm (for ethephon dose 1.57 g/l) and 0.7 cm (for ethephon dose 2.10 g/l) and for 1 min immersion time for the two varieties of *C. limon*.

- The hard spots of CBS symptoms induced on fruit peels were confirmed to be caused by *P. citricarpa* by RT-PCR.

Figure 1.

Sub-Task 2.1.2. Experiments in countries where the pathogen is NOT known to be present: Italy and Greece.

1. No CBS symptoms were developed on ethephon treated fruits (Fig. 2).
2. The spots/lesions developed on some fruits treated with ethephon were caused by other fungi (e.g., *Alternaria* spp., *Colletotrichum* spp., *Phomopsis* spp.)
3. Some of the treated fruits exhibited rind breakdown because of the long incubation period (35 d).

Fig.2.

Task 2.2. Development and validation of a protocol for the stimulation of fungal growth for detection of *P. citricarpa* (and *P. paracitricarpa*) on green citrus leaves (Meyer et al., 2012)

By the Wet-Dry Technique (Meyer et al., 2012), fungal mycelial mass is enriched and fruiting body formation on the leaf is stimulated (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3.

The first analyses were done by morphological observation (stereomicroscope), but this method is very time-consuming and the fungal structures are difficult to evaluate. For these reasons, an effective, fast, and sensitive protocol for DNA extraction from "wet and dry" leaves has been developed, for molecular detection of the pathogen.

Application of the molecular test to naturally infected samples: the developed method was tested on asymptomatic lemon fruit provided by ISA-CM (Tunisia). 1- upon arrival, the asymptomatic fruits were separated from those with visible symptoms; 2- the presence of *P. citricarpa* was confirmed by molecular analysis of the CBS lesions; 3- Five pools, consisting of three symptomless fruits each, were analysed with the developed method: *P. citricarpa* was detected in all the 5 samples, confirming the effectiveness of the method.

WP 3. Validation of molecular detection of *P. citricarpa* in asymptomatic fruits and leaves

Task 3.1 – Development of a molecular test. Efficacy Evaluation by Real time PCR.

The method tested on asymptomatic fruits artificially inoculated with *P. citricarpa* was efficient and able to detect the pathogen even on one inoculation point in three symptomless fruits.

The analytical specificity of the test against *P. citriasiana* was verified. Sensitivity was validated and confirmed at 10 fg of purified genomic *P. citricarpa* DNA (validation data present in the EPPO database).

Sensitivity evaluation (limit of detection) was evaluated and was confirmed up to 15 g of matter (leaf litter and “wet and dry” leaves) and up to 39 g of matter for peel fruit.

Task 3.2. Test Performance Study of molecular test on asymptomatic tissues

Twelve participants reported results as expected from the preliminary study, one participant reported results for two samples that were not in accordance with expectations.

Both tests evaluated showed good performance, being highly repeatable and reproducible. The PC test (van Gent-Pelzer et al., 2007), as expected, reacted with *P. citricarpa* and *P. paracitricarpa* isolates included in the sample panel. It reacted also with *P. citriasiana*, but the results were not highly reproducible. The Pc-TEF1 test showed high specificity and reacted with *P. citricarpa* isolates only. The Pc-TEF1 test can be used for confirmation of the *P. citricarpa* in samples positive with PC test. The FQ test can be used as control test for confirmation of successful extraction of DNA from fungi in the sample.

All three tests showed high repeatability (> 95%) and reproducibility (> 96%) and can be used for testing of DNA extracted from citrus fruit peel. PC and Pc-TEF test showed high specificity (100% and 98%, respectively).

2.5. Conclusions and recommendations to policy makers

The proposed method using Ethephon can be useful in infested countries for orchards investigations to anticipate maturation and appearance of symptoms but not for border inspections of imported citrus fruit in countries where the pathogen is not present because it's time-consuming and not effective on already-ripe fruits.

The developed qPCR-based method for *P. citricarpa* detection showed high specificity and reacted with *P. citricarpa* isolates only. The test can be used for confirmation of the *P. citricarpa* in samples positive with other tests.

2.6. Benefits from trans-national cooperation

International collaboration among laboratories of countries in which the disease is present and those in which it is not, has made it possible to evaluate important aspects for the purposes of controlling the disease, especially at the entry points of imported citrus fruits and in the countries of origin before 'export.

Research activity and validation of the results between laboratories in different countries has led to the standardization of molecular methods for specific detection of the causal agent of the disease, allowing the implementation of diagnostic protocols in order to update the EPPO standards.

3. Outreach

3.1. Article(s) for publication in journals

Zajc, J., Zwitter, Z.K., Fišer, S., Gostinčar, C., Vicent, A. & Domenech, A.G. et al. (2023). Highly specific qPCR and amplicon sequencing method for detection of quarantine citrus pathogen *Phyllosticta citricarpa* applicable for air samples. *Plant Pathology*, 72, 548–563. Available from: <https://doi.org/10.1111/ppa.13679>

3.2. Grey literature

Express Pest Risk Analysis for “*Phyllosticta citricarpa*”, edited by: Brunetti A., Pirone L., Valente M.T. 2023. CREA – Research Centre for Plant Protection and Certification, Rome, Italy.

3.3. Events

None.

4. Open Euphresco data

Brunetti A., Pirrone L, Valente MT (2023). Express PRA for Italy: *Phyllosticta citricarpa* (McAlpine) van der Aa. Available from <https://drop.euphresco.net/data/60bdedb1-0e62-4f96-8fb1-e82c51108044/>